

Farmonov F.F¹. Kodirov T.J².

¹Bukhara State Technical University,
Uzbekistan, Bukhara region, 200100, Bukhara, Q. Murtazaev street, 15, bstu_info@edu.uz

²Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry,
Tashkent city, Republic of Uzbekistan Address:100100, Tashkent, st. Shokhjahan, 5,
<https://ttysi.uz/oz>

E-mail: feruzfarmonov831@gmail.com ,

Abstract. The study used a physical method, namely laser modification, in addition to chemical treatments, to produce Wet-Blue leather semi-finished products. Laser treatment accelerates the formation of reactive radicals by opening various bonds in the skin tissue, and during subsequent treatment, these reactive radicals and chromium-containing complex compounds enter into a chemical reaction. It was confirmed that the Wet-Blue sheepskin leather semi-finished product has improved physical and mechanical properties when treated with laser light before tanning. The tensile strength was found to be 25.0% higher than that of the Wet-Blue sheepskin leather semi-finished product produced using traditional technology.

Keywords: collagen, dermis, laser irradiation, chromium, tanning, Wet-Blue, hydrothermal destruction, tensile strength, elongation at break.

ENTER.

Tanning is a key process in the leather manufacturing process, which is the treatment of the collagen fiber structure of the leather, mainly with a tanner (a type of cross-linked protein), which makes it more hygienically durable and durable [1].

Wet-Blue refers to the intermediate stage of the chromium salt tanning process, in which the hides are only chrome-tanned, wet, and blue in color. [2]

Chromium salts are the only tanning agent that produces the most desirable properties of leather [3]. Pankova and others.[4] developed a technology for plasma-chemical finishing of natural leather using silver nanoparticles and low-pressure HF plasma. An induction high-frequency plasmatron was developed for processing nanoparticles in an inductive discharge. The use of this technology has been found to significantly increase the quality of leather texture of natural leather, in particular, to significantly improve their physical and mechanical properties.

In the work [5], the high efficiency of the chrome tanning process of leather using ultrasound is shown. The tanning technology is described, and the new process allows to reduce the time required for tanning and obtain a higher quality material from it.

One of the new promising directions in skin tissue modification is its treatment with laser light. The advantage of this method is that it radically changes the structure of its fibers and increases their activity towards chemicals[6].

The main parameters of laser rays affecting the natural skin are its wavelength, power and density. In the first pulse of the laser, the water molecule in the skin structure evaporates, the temperature rises in the layer near the surface, and an area of reduced internal air pressure is formed, which makes it possible to use the energy of the second pulse more fully for laser ablation [7].

Methodological part.

Sample preparation. An average sample is obtained by conducting chemical tests and physico-mechanical experiments on a small amount of substances and materials. Samples are taken based on state standards.

1. For chemical analysis.
2. For physico-mechanical experiments.

For each test, a sample is taken from the right and left side of the skin. For physical-mechanical experiments, the skin samples cut out are numbered and the upper, lower, and marginal parts are indicated by arrows.

The sample taken for chemical testing is weighed and ground to an “error of no more than 0.01 g.” The sample obtained is tested according to GOST-938-75 [8].

Hydrothermal destruction was determined according to GOST 938.25 [2].

Tensile strength limit, stress at the formation of cracks in the surface layer of leather, elongation at break, elongation and conditional tensile modulus at a stress of 9.8 MPa GOST 938.11. determined according to [2].

Laser irradiation. In this work, a sample of Wet-Blue semi-finished leather was treated with laser in a double-pulse mode. A 1064 nm yttrium aluminum garnet LS-2134D laser was used, generating in a double-pulse mode (pulses separated by a time interval of 3 μ s, pulse duration 10 ns)[3].

Conclusion and discussion.

Taking into account the above studies, we set ourselves the task of applying new generation laser technology to our research, which gives complex properties to the Wet-Blue leather semi-finished product. Laser technology has not been widely used in the production of leather products. Laser radiation has a coherent monochromatic collimation, which is its peculiarity. The interaction of laser radiation with skin tissues is based on its physical properties [2].

Therefore, the main task is to select the optimal parameters of laser irradiation that will give new intensive properties to the Wet-Blue leather semi-product. In this case, the semi-product of sheep Wet-Blue leather processed by standard technology was treated with laser beams with an energy interval of 20–30 J for 20–40 seconds, and its hydrothermal destruction was determined. These parameters showed that laser modification led to morphological changes in the dermis structure.

Hydrothermal destruction of semi-finished leather samples of laser-modified Wet-Blue in different modes is presented in Figure 1. Hydrothermal destruction of semi-finished sheep Wet-Blue leather was achieved at a temperature of 95°C in the control sample and 97°C in the experimental samples.

Figure 1 - Changes in hydrothermal destruction of laser-modified Wet-Blue sheepskin semi-finished product after tanning process.

Laser treatment of semi-finished sheep Wet-Blue leather samples allowed to obtain high values of hydrothermal destruction. It was found that the destruction temperature of the modified semi-finished Wet-Blue leather samples was 2.1% higher than the control sample. Based on the data obtained, we can conclude that the laser modification of the Wet-Blue leather semi-finished product caused the reaction of the non-reactive lysing compounds with the fabrics.

Naturally, one of the indicators for assessing the quality of Wet-Blue leather semi-finished products is their strength and elongation at break, as the leather produced must be strong and elastic. Therefore, the elongation at break and tensile strength of the control and experimental samples of tanned Wet-Blue leather semi-finished products were determined using a YG026T tensile machine by cutting standard samples, and the results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Physical and mechanical properties of laser-modified Wet-Blue sheepskin semi-finished products

Indicators	Control sample	Laser modified samples		
		<i>E=20J, T=30 cek.</i>	<i>E=25J, T=30 cek.</i>	<i>E=30J, T=30 cek.</i>
Hydrothermal destruction, °C	95,0	95,7	97,0	96,3
Tensile strength limit, MPa	12,0	13,5	15,0	14,0
Elongation in tension, %	23,0	25,0	31,0	28,0

It was found that the tensile strength and elongation at stress in the control sample modified by laser irradiation with 25 J energy for 30 seconds increased by 25.0% and 34.78%, respectively, compared to the Wet-Blue leather semi-finished product produced by the traditional technology.

The morphological structures of the experimental and control samples of Wet-Blue leather semi-finished products were studied using a digital optical trinocular microscope (KXL-2001) at 200x magnification(Figure 2). This study made it possible to identify certain features of the effect of laser

irradiation on the morphological structure of leather tissues.

a)

b)

Figure 2. Morphological structure of the Wet-Blue leather semi-finished product: (a) control sample; (b) experimental sample after laser irradiation (200× magnification, digital optical trinocular microscope KXL-2001)

Conclusion. Based on the above results, it can be concluded that when the Wet-Blue leather semi-finished product is treated with laser irradiation, it acquires improved physico-mechanical properties. Furthermore, changes occur in the structural elements of the leather tissue, accompanied by structural softening, surface relief modification, variations in the thickness of individual collagen fibers, and their separation into bundles.

LITERATURE

1. Kanagaraj J., Senthilvelan T., Panda R.C., Kavitha S. Eco-friendly waste management strategies for greener environment towards sustainable development in leather industry: A comprehensive review. // *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 2015. 89, -P.1–17
2. Farmanov F.F, Kodirov T.J, Toshev A.Y, Azimov J.Sh, Murodov T.B. .Research of the influence of laser modification on the physical-mechanical properties of Wet-Blue leather semi-product. // *international journal of advanced research in science, engineering and technology(IJARSET)*. ISSN: 2350-0328. Vol. 11, Issue 10, oktober 2024. P.22330-22336..
3. Kadirov T.J, Farmonov F.F, Toshev A.Y, Shoyimov Sh.Sh. Study of physical and mechanical properties of Wet-Blue leather semi-finished products processed by laser irradiation./ *Scientific-technical and practical Journal of compositional materials*. №3/2023.-P.64-68
4. Pankova, E. A., Rakhmatullina, G. R., & Parsanov, A. S. Development of plasma-chemical finishing technology for natural leathers // *Bulletin of Kazan Technological University*, 2017. – 20. № 9. P. 60-62.
5. Anisovich, A. G., Markevich, M. I., Zhuravleva, V. I., Kodirov, T. Zh., Khudanov, U. O.. Morphology of the surface of vegetable-tanned natural leather after ultrasonic treatment and laser exposure. // *Nondestructive Testing and Diagnostics*, № 2, 2023.P.154–157.
6. Kodirov, T. Zh., Markevich, M. I., Malyshko, A. N., & Zhuravleva, V. I. (n.d.). Structure and elemental composition of a sample of natural leather under laser irradiation.,P 56–58.
7. Toshev A., Kodirov T. Synthesis and Research of Thermostability of Stabilized Acrylic Emulsion for Finishing Dyeing in Leather Dressing // *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, – 2020. – Vol. 29, – No. 5. – P. 12547-12555.
8. Ostrovskaya, A. V., Abdullin, I. Sh., & Shagivilieva, R. R. (2006). *Chemistry and Technology of*

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-9

Leather and Fur: A Textbook. Kazan. p. 139.

